

Traces: Doing mathematics, and the mathematics that is done to us

Jean-François Maheux, Université du Québec à Montréal, maheux.jean-francois@uqam.ca

Carl Andre once wrote that “Art is what we do; culture is what is done to us.” Might not the same be said about mathematics? In this study, I focus on “traces” to show how mathematics is both and simultaneously something we do and something that is done to us. In so doing, I articulate how this conceptualisation allows us to fully include the cultural historical dimension of mathematics while theorizing mathematics as doing, rather than something we teach, learn, know or understand.

Overview

We are familiar with the distinction between doing mathematics (when we solve problems, look for patterns, search for proof, create and apply methods, etc.), and learning about mathematics (when mathematics is a set of “facts”, ideas and procedures to memorize or understand, and so on). Papert’s (1972) went so far as to say:

Being a mathematician is no more definable as ‘knowing’ a set of mathematical facts than being a poet is definable as knowing a set of linguistic facts. Some modern mathematical education reformers will give this statement a too easy assent with the comment: ‘Yes, they must understand, not merely know’. But this misses the capital point that being a mathematician, again like being a poet, or a composer or an engineer, means *doing*, rather than knowing or understanding. (p. 249)

When I heard about artist Carl Andre’s (2004) aphorism, “Art is what we do; culture is what is done to us” (p. 23), it made me think about these two dimensions in relation to mathematics. Mathematics as a practice implies both doing mathematics and mathematics being done to us. When working on a problem, there is a part where we exert control, freely decide what move we try, and navigate our way through. But we do this with concepts and rules established before us, that are then “imposed” (or “imposes themselves”) on our activity. More so, one can argue that every step we take while doing mathematics also “frames” our next (possible) move. We are thus simultaneously both active and passive subjects in relation to mathematics.

In this paper I theoretically and empirically reflect on the relationship between what we do and what is done to us mathematically as a driving force in mathematics (education). I also present it as a way to include the cultural historical dimension of mathematics through an analysis of mathematical activity in terms of “traces” (Serre, 2002) to conceptualize how mathematics “reproduces” in time and space.

Please cite as: Maheux, J.-F. (2021). Traces: Doing mathematics, and the mathematics that is done to us. In D. Kollosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 2, pp. 622–631). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5415312>

Conceptualizations of mathematics, cognition and learning

In the 1990's many scholars in mathematics education were debating between the "cognitive" view of learning and teaching and the newly emerging "participative" conceptualization. One emphasized the active construction of mathematical understanding by individual students in the line of radical constructivism, while the other insisted on how learning and teaching are better viewed as taking part in certain practices historically, culturally and contextually situated. Naturally, many tried to overcome the conundrum. Sfard (1998) for example took a pragmatic approach, suggesting us both "metaphors" alternatively or in combination. One problem with this is that these conceptualizations rest on deeply incompatible, even competitive epistemologies. To elude the quandary, Sfard (2015) eventually develop her own theory, based on the notion of internal/external discourses.

But in the 2000's a new line of thinking started to take wind, so to speak, offering a radically different take on the matter by insisting on the "body" (see Sinclair & Freitas, 2019). Increasingly complex conceptualizations emerged, for example Roth's (2011) distinction between body and "flesh", or de Freitas and Sinclair's (2014) (none-human) "material bodies" agentivity. These theories often manage to address phenomena of interest to cognitive, participative or discursive approaches in their own light.

Of course, this is only a fraction of the theoretical work done in the last decades addressing these (and other) dichotomies. One can think for example about the writings of Radford and his theory of objectification, or Brown's uses of psychoanalysis. We are also familiar with Walkerdine's approach to subjectivity, and many might know of Pais' exploration of Hegel's philosophy. Another relevant if perhaps less notorious line of thinking can also be found in Luitel's notion of "im/pure knowledge", and some reflections on tools and technology in relation with the nature of doing/knowing mathematics also invited us to question our epistemologies.

As part of this tradition, my colleague Jérôme Proulx and I began to develop in the 2010's our approach to mathematics education with a radical proposition of our own: to completely put aside all notions related to knowledge, knowing, teaching and learning (see, e.g., Maheux & Proulx 2015, 2017). The central notion for us is that of "doing" mathematics, a focus on mathematical activity that includes closely attending to (a) all the means by which people observably do mathematics (in writing, speech, gestures, with diagrams or various technologies and so on), and (b) the emergent nature mathematical activity (e.g., in "problem solving", which we describe as *problematizing mathematically*). One aspect that recently grasped our attention is the notion of "trace" as a mean to describe and explain for example the geographical-historical spread of mathematics as well as what ordinarily happen in a mathematics classroom. In this paper, I illustrate this conceptualization by a short analysis, while arguing that mathematics is both and simultaneously something we do and something that is done to us. Moreover, I argue that these qualities are essential to the *propagation* of mathematics when traces of mathematical activities trigger mathematical activity in response, which generates more traces, and so on.

Traces in/of mathematical activity

The concept of trace is coextensive with the living in general: As soon as there is referral to another or to something else, there is a trace
Jacques Derrida (2002, p. 127)

The above quotation by Jacques Derrida outlines the importance of “traces” in human experiences (and more). For Derrida, a trace is fundamentally some thing that makes present something other than itself. If I write $\frac{16}{64}$, what stands beside me is *not* a number (in itself), but marks of ink on paper that evokes the idea of a number I can also invoke by writing $\frac{1}{4}$, 0.25, or by saying “a quarter” and so on. None of these concretely observable traces contain the number and yet, they are (for me and you) a way for it to appear (and become part of an activity, should it only be that of recognizing the number)¹. One famous study of this distinction is Magritte’s painting *The treachery of images*, in which we see a pipe and sentence that reads “This is not a pipe” (see Foucault’s 1983 book-length analysis). We can easily think of various analogues of this in relation to mathematics, for example:

$$\frac{16}{64} = \frac{1}{4}$$

This is not mathematics

Figure 1. The treachery of traces of mathematical activity

A trace can be a written word, a drawing, a spoken sound, but also the alteration of something. Serre (2002) alerts us to the lack of attention given to traces, and un-exhaustively discuss four kinds of traces: (1) imprints, like a footprint in the sand, (2) after-effects, like the aftermath of a hurricane, (3) remanent, like a tiny quantity of poison or alcohol in the blood, and (4) inscriptions, like symbols and writings. It is important to insist on how the notion of trace differs from what we generally see in semiotics for example. Traces are not “signs” or “index”, they do not “stand for” something (as in Pierce’s theory), nor are they linguistically defined (as in de Saussure’s approach). Semiology offers invaluable insights in relation to traces, and scholars in mathematics education explored many of its possibilities (Duval’s theory of semiotics representations for example). But these approaches are rarely compatible with the epistemological posture I outlined in the previous section, in which metaphysical entities are denied in the benefit of actual acts.

Closer to us, Bakhtin (e.g., 1981) conceptualizes the process of signification through which meaning is not only never pre-determined, but also always open, and attached not to signs but to full (chains of) utterances. Signs are intentional traces, but as traces what matters is the whole activity in which they are involved. Traces can then be seen as “operations” (Derrida, 1967, p. 71), and when Derrida says that “as soon as there is referral to another or

¹ As we will see, I am not suggesting here that numbers or other mathematical objects exist elsewhere, beyond our reference to them, but a full discussion of their emergent nature goes beyond what I can discuss here: see Maheux & Proulx (2014) for some insights. Similarly, a deeper philosophical discussion on the concept of trace is evidently in order.

to something else, there is a trace”, it is the *act* of referring we should think about. More so, the operation goes in two directions (often at once): Traces are the product of some activity, and they also produce some activity. When I write $\frac{16}{64} = \frac{1}{4}$, I am generally mathematically active. The mark is a result of my mathematical thinking. And when I read the equation, I am also generally mathematically active, I am doing mathematics when I interpret it as an equality, two equivalent fractions, two ways of writing the same number, the result of a simplification, and so on. The word “generally” is important. It precisely reminds us that tracing or looking at $\frac{16}{64} = \frac{1}{4}$ does not necessarily imply doing mathematics. I need a special kind of orientation or better: I need to *do* certain kind of things with it.

In the following section, the analysis of a short fragment of a classroom lesson continues to present this perspective while bringing about aspects of how mathematics is both something we do and something that is done to us.

In the classroom

The point of philosophy is to start with something so simple as not to seem worth stating, and to end with something so paradoxical that no one will believe it.
 Bertrand Russel (1918, p. 193)

The following episode takes place near the 20th minute of a lesson. Mary switches to a fresh page on the whiteboard, and as she speaks writes up in large characters $\frac{16}{64}$:

- Mary: Here I have sixteen over sixty-four, and I found that when I cross out the six's I get one fourth. Does this method work? Yes? Why?
- Samy: Because you do four times six, it gives you sixty-four. If you do times six you get the same answer.
- Mary: Okay, if you do one times...
- Samy: Eh no, time 16.

Figure 2. Fragment of a classroom lesson

This provides us with a simple example of what we usually think in terms of how written traces come about in classroom mathematics activity. Mary uses the board to keep track of what she says, and the written traces apparently serve more or less the same purpose as the speech: make something available to students’ consideration. The offer here seems to be the mathematical proposition of a “method” presented through an example, and students are asked to react. But *how* is this actually taking place?

If we slow down the production of Mary’s “first” trace (in a series of many), we can appreciate its mathematical density. To make sense of what she writes and says, one needs to be able to use base 10 positional system for writing and naming numbers. These are, of course, cultural-historical constructs. The base 10 system draws on the work of Stevin (in 1585) who wrote a booklet on how “fractional numbers” could be calculated on by expressing them as sums of powers of ten. Stevin’s proposition was then worked on, people talked and wrote about it: in France, a coma was added to separate the integer and the fractional part while the English preferred a dot. It is through all these discourses and inscriptions that this way of writing numbers finally (almost completely) took over the roman systems and made

its way to us. And of course, the idea certainly came to Stevin from reading or hearing about base 10 systems developed before him, the indo-arabic symbols for numbers, and so on.

The same goes for the history of fractional notation, also essential to make sense of what is going on in the classroom that day. We know writings by Diophantus (in Greece around 2000 BC) in which he talks about rational numbers, writings which Abu'l-Wafa (in Iraq around 960) knew and draws on for his work on certain kinds of “fractions”. Bhaskara’s writings (in India about 1150 BC) are also connected to them, and Al Kashi (in Iran around 1400) explicitly developed some of Abu'l-Wafa’s ideas when he finally sets out most of the rules we use today to manipulate rational numbers in that form. From writings to writings, the mathematical idea occupies ground, it propagates in time and space, each occurrence/text having the potential to generate new mathematical activity that will keep the idea alive, and also develop it. These texts are all traces of mathematical activity left by those mathematicians, that provide a ground to work from. Not having to “start over” every time we do mathematics also implies that we need somehow to follow the steps of those who did mathematics before us. Their ideas, ways of thinking, the representations they came up with, their achievements, their mistakes, all that imposes itself on a mathematicians’ work.

Forces are at play and affect us also because mathematically speaking, all ways of writing numbers are not equal. Some representations render specific mathematical work easy or difficult, necessary or impossible, relevant or useless, and so on. Think for example of computing $\frac{3}{10} + \frac{1}{8}$ versus $0.300 + 0.175$, or $\frac{1}{3} \times \frac{2}{5}$ versus $0.333... \times 0.4$.² Forms of writing number can also make apparent or not some of their properties, and encourage us to think and work with them in specific ways (1.61803398875... might not say much, while $\frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}$ or $\sqrt{1+\sqrt{1+\sqrt{1+\dots}}}$ are quite revealing, and inviting!). So by presenting to her students $\frac{16}{64}$ and $\frac{1}{4}$, Mary is not only introducing numbers, but also a certain way of thinking about them, of using them, and so on. The fractional writing alludes to the fact that $\frac{16}{64}$ is *two* numbers that combine to express *one*, that we can also write $\frac{1}{4}$ (or 0.25 for that matter), and so on. This can be seen as one of the ways mathematics *imposes itself* upon us. We never “directly access” mathematical ideas like numbers, but only encounter “traces” that are evocative, and these traces, shaped by history, are related to ways of thinking and ways of doing mathematically. They are not neutral manifestations, but tainted way to bring forth. So much so, could we say, that we dedicate years of study (e.g., at elementary school) to be able to make sense of them. This is also why we strongly react to the suggestion of crossing out the six: this is not how we use that form of writing, but it’s also this form of writing that makes possible thinking we might do so. One might even argue that this possibility is itself imposed (as a possibility), and that is why students often came up with undesired ways of manipulating fractions: maybe the writing itself (and the fact that we do for multiplications) invites us to do $\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} = \frac{2}{6}$ by adding numerators and denominators?

²Another great example is how the Ancient Egyptian *had to* transform all fractions into a sum of unit fractions because that’s the way their system worked ($\frac{3}{10}$ would be written as $\frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{10}$), while we *can* express any rational number in an infinite number of ways ($\frac{3}{10} = \frac{30}{100} = \frac{15}{50}$ and so on).

Of course, such imposition does not mean there is no room to maneuver, on the contrary. When I hear or see $\frac{16}{64}$, I am not *forced* to do mathematics with it (some of my students quite often prove it), nor to work with it in a completely specific way. I *could*, for example, be looking for an equivalent fraction by first dividing $16 \div 64$ to find 0.25 and then write that as $\frac{25}{100}$, or do 0.25×8 to find 2, and thus $\frac{2}{8}$ and so on. I can even “misinterpret” what is in front of me, or make “little mistakes” when working with it: for example, saying “times six” when I mean “time sixteen”, or thinking for a moment that “doing times six” has the same counter-effect as “crossing out” a six digit. What mathematics does is setting us up in a certain way (see Heidegger, 1953).

It gets more complicated because “instantiations” of mathematical ideas are not randomly found, but come from the active work of someone... who is also setting us up. Here, Mary is not only introducing numbers in a certain way, she also seems to be doing it for the purpose of illustrating a “method”, and that is only as part of another endeavor (e.g., leading a math lesson) that is part of another (e.g., teaching junior high math to this group of teenagers) and so on. All these layers of activity are in a way piled up in her utterance, and part of what it comes to mean for us or for the students that day. The marks on the board and the words she spoke do not merely contain or in themselves assert all of these, but they are complicit to all (or some) of that. They at the least take part in the “normality” of all that is taking place, and even a relatively disruptive proposition such as simplifying fractions by removing numbers hardly goes against that. The mathematics done to us when we “do mathematics” in class is of a certain kind: we have a way of attending to mathematical traces, intentions and all kinds of procedures that are quite specific to school mathematical *genre* (as conceptualized by Bakhtin for instance). Doing mathematics in school is not exactly the same everywhere of course, but still significantly differs from what professional mathematicians do at the university or in workplaces. The case of “weird fractions” such as $\frac{16}{64}$ is a good example of that. We can see in the literature mathematicians such as Boas (1973) or Stufflebeam (2013) work with them very differently than a teacher does (see, for example, Johnson, 1985). But again, it is only through such concrete actions and all the traces that they leave that ways of doing mathematics realize themselves.

The other aspect to consider here some more is how mathematical traces can generate mathematical activity in return. When we see something like $\frac{16}{64}$, we are not obligated to mathematically engage with it, but those of us who encountered that kind of writing over and over again almost instantly recognize it, and are somehow compelled to read it as a fraction, to “understand it”. This is in a way related to how traces are always missing something: they are “negative spaces” that *we* need to fill. The necessity for interpretation, for signification, implies that we need to do mathematics for mathematics to be done to us. If I flip the pages of a book, and my eye catches numbers but I do nothing with them, or if I sit in the back of the classroom and play on my phone while I hear the teacher present something on the board, little seems to happen in terms of mathematics being done/to me. The book or the class could be on any subject, it would make no difference. But when I engage in mathematical “meaning making”, when I begin to *do* mathematics, this is when it

all takes place. And more precisely, this is when *mathematics* takes place. For hundreds of years, Sumerian clay tablets were nothing but rugged rocks in the sand, until we began again to *respond* to them in reading (thinking mathematically) and writing (e.g., to explain the mathematics that has been done). Responding is a great way to describe what happens because it suggests both being affected by what we respond to, and affecting it by giving that something an actual signification. Whether saying “she is a number!” is a compliment or an insult actually rests not on the utterer, but on how we (e.g., the person called that way) respond to it (“and proud of it!”, or “you should look at yourself!” or “what do you mean?”, etc.). The response might have a verbal or gestural aspect to it, but we should also include here emotional responses for example, whether or not they are observable from the outside. Responses immediately offer themselves as something to be responded to, should it be by oneself (e.g., thoughts: this is what Husserl was so interested in) or others, in the case of observable responses.

Tangible responses-traces also have the advantage of being easier to follow. In the fragment above, we can see how Samy’s utterance as a response to Mary’s proposition. We can also recognize it as a mathematical response, meaning that Mary’s utterance was “good enough” to generate some mathematical activity. Indeed, what Samy offers sounds to us as if he really attended to what Mary said and wrote, and what he articulates looks like the traces of some “mental” mathematical activity. In a way, his response is the result of mathematics being done to him, and we can pinpoint many aspects of his sentence that align with the kind of mathematics being done, and the writings and talk he was exposed to. His answer uses some of the numbers (names) used by Mary (“four”, “sixty-four”) and the idea of performing something on the numbers of the first fraction to obtain those of the second (“you get the same answer”). The presence of a “six” in Samy proposition (“you do four times six, it gives you sixty-four”) is suggestive: Samy corrects himself (“eh no, times 16”), but the emphasis on the sixes in Mary’s utterance could very well explain why he would think for a second that this might be the number he needed, thereby not only offering an answer to whether or not the method works ($\frac{16}{64}$ is the same as $\frac{1}{4}$ since...), but also why that is (i.e., removing the 6 is the opposite of multiplying by 6). And let’s not forget that pragmatically, it is also by responding in such a way that Samy gives mathematical meaning to Mary’s utterance³. And of course, Mary’s response to Samy is doing just the same. From turn to turn, the trace on the board slowly grows, nourished by other traces of the ongoing mathematical activity. Figure 3 shows the board later on.

Figure 3. The board later on

³ There is a famous sketch in which Costello “proves” that $28 \div 7 = 13$ and $13 \times 7 = 28$ (e.g., <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xkbQDEXJy2k>). Costello’s writings are in many ways similar to what Mary was doing, but the answer to his performance is generally quite different!

A lot can be said about how traces on that board enabled and constrained the mathematics taking place. We see in the middle right a $\frac{\times 16}{\times 16}$ that followed Samy's correction, which leads to a discussion on why both fractions are equivalent. On the left, $\frac{25}{52} \neq \frac{2}{2}$ is what remains of the examination of a counter-example that also served to clearly distinguish two kinds of fractions: those that work with the method and those that don't (notice the rectangles drawn around both cases and the yes/no ("Oui", "Non") label added on top). The class then moved on to examine $\frac{64}{16} = \frac{4}{1}$ following a student reaction, and this case made it relevant to explain what the fraction $\frac{4}{1}$ meant (hence the added "= 4"), and why that fraction is not really different from the $\frac{64}{16}$ (hence the arrow). Next, Mary suggested to consider $\frac{24}{48} = \frac{2}{8}$ as another case of fractions that works, and a student pointed out that again, ultimately, the fraction $\frac{1}{4}$ was involved. Based on that, a discussion could have developed on whether all weird fractions are equivalent to $\frac{1}{4}$, but this was not the case. The class instead clarified the distinction between an equivalent fraction using smaller numbers (2 and 8 instead of 24 and 48) and the most reduced fraction (when no factors remain common to the numerator and the denominator). That discussion seems to have put some students on the path of new weird fractions in the form of $\frac{10}{100}$ (at the bottom), for which they actually could articulate why digits could be canceled out.

At that point, the board was full, and Mary had to switch to a fresh screen. The initial mark led to the production of so many other marks, all traces of and for mathematical activity, and there was no room left to write. The propagation illustrated in this spreading also connects with that of the mathematical ideas among the people in the room. More and more students contributed to the issue set up by Mary's opening proposition and, being express in such a publicly accessible manner, each of their ideas could reach all people in the room. Mary's "transcription" on the board of what students suggested continuously contributed to that: as a response, it validated them as relevant to the specific issue being addressed and to the whole of what was going on at the time (i.e. a mathematics lesson). But Mary's writing was also more akin to a *translation*: she interpreted the talk and offered specific mathematical ways to work with what she heard. For example, Samy's suggestions, in the fragment above, was turned into $\frac{\times 16}{\times 16}$ on the board, while Mary rephrased what Samy said as "ok ok so if you do time sixteen on bottom and on top we will get sixteen over sixty-four", clearly adding her own interpretation to his spoken words.

Moving on to a clean board, the traces of the first part of the classroom's work were no longer visible. But they were still very present, of course, and continued to affect what was going on. Mary even switched back between screens a few times. With today's technology, erasure becomes less permanent. In the past, traces of mathematical activity had to be carefully preserved. We know about Sumerian, Egyptian or Greek mathematics because some (often rare) texts were conserved. This is how the mathematical work of scribes and engineers could reach us, could be kept, taken on and developed. Nowadays, the iterability of traces almost creates the opposite problem: So much mathematical work is available that

contributions risk getting lost like drops in the sea. And on the other hand, it means that “mathematical mistakes” are also potentially more visible.

For the classroom, this raises questions. The mathematics we have done before is of course essential to the continuation of our mathematical activity today, should it only be in the traces it left “within us” (the memories we can recall, the ways of thinking we’ve become accustomed to, the methods we practiced and can now use, etc.). But the possibility for old traces of one’s mathematical activity to come forth, be exposed, become other’s object of attention is also a risk! We know that *all* mathematicians make mistakes now and then, and some of those are even famous... but we also live in a world where making mistakes is not as highly valued as we could wish (see for example Brown, 1993). And we could easily connect this with mathematical “trauma” (e.g., Lange & Meaney, 2011) that are other kinds of traces (sequels, scars) of mathematics being done/to us...

Last words: Doing mathematics, Husserl, Deleuze, and others

As I am running out of space, I want to conclude by highlighting how this study really rests on a very specific epistemology of mathematics. This perspective focuses on “doing mathematics” to the extent that what happens in school is no longer a matter of teaching and learning, but simply seen as opportunities for people to do mathematics together, and so doing encounter other people’s work, and become familiar with mathematical ways of thinking, of doing, with mathematical ideas and so on (see again Maheux & Proulx, 2017). What we mean by the adjective “mathematical” here is crucial. Drawing on the conceptualization put forth by Husserl (see in Derrida, 1989) when he tells us that “geometry is on its way to its origin”, we see mathematics as something that is still in the making, open-ended, boundless, and thus cannot really be defined (from the Latin *de-* “completely” + *finire* “to bound, limit”). Another way to see it is in Deleuze’s (1994) infinite cycle of differences and repetitions in the course of which certain ways of being or doing take shape, but also continuously transform. Mathematics for us is a movement that goes in a way we can (here and now) recognize as mathematical (thereby contributing to what being mathematical “means”). A movement that leaves traces in its passage, spurs we are bound to follow, a direction only us can travel.

To all this, one might rightfully ask “but how do you consider the political and economic dimensions of school mathematics?” First, it is important to insist that I offer here a way to look at what is going on in school on an ordinary basis. I believe we can think of and examine various kind of classroom settings and management precisely asking “how is mathematics done (to us)” in this case? And I would suggest doing so not in hope of finding the right or the best way to do it, but rather in the spirit of appreciating potentials and advocate for diversity in the mathematical experiences offered to students. Politics is about empowerment, the possibility to do things. While reforming a school system or changing well established practices might sound like don Quixote’s impossible dream, realizing that one actually *does* mathematics in a certain way, and that other ways of doing could be *included* without replacing everything is, in my view, a powerful move. Thinking in terms of doing

mathematics (how it is done, what it does, how it propagates and develop) rather than focusing only on “teaching” and “learning” can at least create the practical opportunity to enrich our discourses, and thus bring into light certain power to act essential political concerns and change, as articulated by Arendt for example.

References

- Andre, C. (2004). [Untitled entry]. In P. Gale (Ed.), *Artists Talk: 1969–1977* (pp. 10–31). Halifax: Press of the Nova Scotia College of Art and Design. (Original work published 1969)
- Bakhtin, M. (1981). *Towards a philosophy of the act*. University of Texas Press.
- Boas, R. P. (1972). Anomalous cancellation. *The Two-Year College Mathematics Journal*, 3(2), 21–24.
- Brown, S. I. (1993). Towards a pedagogy of confusion. In A. M. White (Ed.), *Essays in humanistic mathematics* (pp. 107–122). The Mathematical Association of America.
- de Freitas, E., & Sinclair, N. (2014). *Mathematics and the body: Material entanglements in the classroom*. Cambridge University Press.
- Deleuze, G. (1994). *Difference and repetition*. Columbia University Press.
- Derrida, J. (2002). *Trace et archive, image et art*. INA.
- Derrida, J. (1989). *Edmund Husserl’s origin of geometry*. University of Nebraska Press.
- Foucault, M. (1983). *This is not a pipe*. University of California Press.
- Heidegger, M. (1993). *The question concerning technology*. In D. Farrell Krell (Ed.) *Martin Heidegger: Basic writings* (pp. 311–341). Routledge. (Original work published 1953)
- Johnson, E. (1985). Algebraic and numerical explorations inspired by the simplification $16/64=1/4$. *Focus on Learning Problems in Mathematics*, 7(3-4), 15–28.
- Lange, T., & Meaney, T. (2011). I actually started to scream: Emotional and mathematical trauma from doing school mathematics homework. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 77(1), 35–51.
- Maheux, J. F. & Proulx, J. (2017). Mathematics education (research) liberated from teaching and learning: Towards (the future of) doing mathematics. *The Mathematics Enthusiast*, 15(6), 78–99.
- Maheux, J. F. & Proulx, J. (2014). Doing|mathematics: Analysing data with/in an enactivist-inspired approach. *ZDM Mathematics Education*, 47(2), 211–221.
- Papert, S. (1972). Teaching children to be mathematicians versus teaching about mathematics. *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, 3(3), 249–262.
- Roth, W. M. (2011). *Geometry as objective science in elementary school classrooms: Mathematics in the flesh*. Routledge.
- Russell, B. (1956). The philosophy of logical atomism. In R. C. Marsh (Ed.), *Logic and Knowledge* (pp. 175–281). Allen & Unwin. (Original work published 1918)
- Serres Alexandre (2002). Quelle(s) problématique(s) de la trace? Communication at the Séminaire du CERCOR. https://archivesic.ccsd.cnrs.fr/sic_00001397
- Sfard, A. (1998). On two metaphors for learning and the dangers of choosing just one. *Educational Researcher*, 27(2), 4–13.
- Sfard, A. (2015). Learning, commognition and mathematics. In D. Scott & E. Hargreaves (Eds.), *The Sage handbook of learning* (pp. 129–138). Sage.
- Sinclair N. & de Freitas, E. (2019). Body studies in mathematics education: Diverse scales of mattering. *ZDM Mathematics Education*, 51, 227–237.
- Stuffelbeam, R. (2013). How weird are weird fractions? *The College Mathematics Journal*, 44(3), 202–209.